

HIERARCHICAL DDoS DETECTION AND RESPONSE IN IOT USING STATEFUL SDN AND MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract: The absence of standards and the diverse nature of the Internet of Things (IoT) have made security and privacy concerns more acute. Attacks such as distributed denial of service (DDoS) are becoming increasingly widespread in IoT, and the need for ways to stop them is growing. The use of newly formed Software-Defined Networking (SDN) significantly lowers the computational burden on IoT network nodes and makes it possible to perform more security measurements. This paper proposes an SDN-based, four module DDoS attack detection and mitigation framework for IoT networks called FMDADM. The proposed FMDADM framework comprises four main modules and five-tier architecture. The first module implements an early detection process based on the average drop rate (ADR) principle using a 32-packet window size. The second module uses a novel double-check mapping function (DCMF), that aids in earlier attack detection at the data plane level. The third module is an ML-based detection application comprising four phases: data preprocessing, feature extraction, training and testing, and classification. This module detects DDoS attacks using only seven features: two selected and five newly computed features. The last module introduces an attack mitigation process. We applied the proposed framework to three test cases: one single-node attack test case and two multi-node attack test cases, all with real IoT traffic generated and deployed in Mininet-IoT. The proposed FMDADM framework efficiently detects DDoS attacks at high and low rates, can discriminate between attack traffic and flash crowds, and protects both local and remote IoT nodes by preventing infection from propagating to the ISP level. The FMDADM outperformed most existing cutting-edge approaches across ten different evaluation criteria. According to the experimental results, FMDADM achieved the following accuracy, precision, F-measure, recall, specificity, negative predictive value, false positive rate, false detection rate, false negative rate, and average detection time benchmarks:- 99.79%, 99.43%, 99.77%, 99.79%, 99.95%, 00.21%, 00.91%, 00.23%, and 2.64 μ s, respectively.

1. INTRODUCTION

The diffusion and integration of the Internet of Things (IOT) into several critical industries, including transportation, healthcare, energy, and agriculture, has become undeniable. IOT is a revolutionary technology that links numerous nodes via wireless technologies to automatically send and receive data. The IOT systems have transformed conventional systems into intelligent, economical, and scalable systems. The heterogeneous nature of IOT networks is a major challenge [1]. This is because various IOT applications have distinct network requirements that must be met to operate the system optimally [2]. In addition to the benefits of IOT services, we have recently noticed their negative consequences on network security. According to Sarker et al. [3], IOT nodes may be vulnerable to malware outbreaks that spread surreptitiously among unprotected nodes to form an enormous number of IOT bot nets. An IOT network's nodes are vulnerable to various attacks that

attempt to obstruct the services offered by the IOT or control the entire network. Among these attack types, distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks can be the IOT system's most challenging security risk [4]. When a DDoS attack is launched against an IOT network, the network immediately begins to allocate resources to handle these requests. Any new requests would be rejected even if they came from a legitimate user, which would prevent the IOT network from providing its services as intended [5]. The most straightforward mitigation strategy is to develop cutting-edge security solutions that safeguard the IOT networks. The main obstacles in deploying any attack detection strategy are the limited power, processing, network bandwidth, and storage capacity resources over different IOT layers [6]. To avoid security breaches, it is critical to protect each layer of the IOT environment. IOT may be attacked at three different layers: the device layer, where data are gathered; the network layer, where data are transported for

processing; and the cloud layer, where data are saved [7]. The proposed framework focuses on IOT network layer security.

In recent years, a range of technologies, systems, and approaches have been proposed for solving security issues in IOT. Software-defined networking (SDN) and machine learning (ML) technologies have attracted the interest of researchers to address different IOT security concerns [8]. On the one hand, a new technique known as “State ful SDN” has expanded the basic functions of Open Flow, the most widely used protocol for communication between data and control planes [9], by adding the ability to apply multiple match-action rules depending on the distinct states detected in the switch’s SDN flow tables [10], [11], [12]. This feature gives the switch the ability to respond to events at the packet level. The switch can take appropriate action if the results of the packet analysis agree with the switch rules listed in the flow tables [13]. Meanwhile, academics have developed many ML-based approaches and strategies for identifying DDOS attacks in SD-IOT. ML-based approaches have yielded good results in detecting DDOS attacks in SD-IOT networks [14]. Building a learned parameter model used to accurately forecast attacks requires training the system on both normal and attack behaviors. A substantial amount of data is produced by an IOT network. Choosing the most pertinent features of a dataset for model training and testing remains a challenging task. Using a large number of features in ML models increases both the cost and time complexity [15]. However, the inclusion of unrelated features renders the model less effective in detecting attacks. The construction of an effective ML-based DDOS detection model depends on the packet feature engineering approach, which is crucial [16], [17]. Considering these factors, we propose a new framework called FMDADM, which comprises four phases: data preprocessing, feature extraction, training and testing, and classification. The proposed FMDADM uses only five new computed features to detect an attack. By using fewer features, attacks can be detected more quickly. A variety of ML models for traffic classification, including Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB), Binomial Logistic Regression (BLR), Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF) classifiers, are used to construct the proposed detection model.

The research questions of our proposed framework can be summarized as follows:

1. Which ML-based DDOS attack detection model is the most suitable for stateful SDN-enabled IOT networks?
2. Which ML-based DDOS attack detection algorithm is best for multi-node attacks in SDN-enabled IOT networks?
3. How can a remote server be protected from bot net attacks over an IOT LAN network?

Whereas the main contributions are as follows:

1. The proposed FMDADM framework employs feature engineering to identify DDOS attacks using only five new computed features. The model can successfully overcome the over-fitting problem and provides a good fit as a result.
 2. The second detection module, which uses a novel proposed mapping function called DCMF, provides two crucial features:- (a) detecting the attack at the data plane level before overwhelming the controller, and (b) discriminating between attack traffic and flash crowds. As a result, the controller has an extra layer of protection against the attack.
 3. A small 32-packet window size is used for feature extraction in the third detection module. The three detection modules resulted in a reduction in the amount of time needed for training, testing, and detection.
 4. FMDADM effectively detects DDOS in multi-node attack scenarios. This is a crucial area of strength for the proposed framework because it is generally known that conventional defenses fall short in the face of these attack scenarios.
 5. FMDADM protects both local and remote IOT nodes by preventing infections from spreading to the ISP level. By protecting the controller and remote nodes in this form, we can stop DDOS attacks before they reach the Internet.
 6. FMDADM uses actual IOT traffic features to build the detection model. Most literature-based studies deal with either simulated traffic or network traffic that is not extracted from actual IO T networks.
 7. According to the experimental results, FMDADM outperformed most of the existing cutting-edge approaches across ten different evaluation criteria.
- The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides a summary of related research on the subject. Section III elaborates the proposed detection framework. The experimental results of the proposed framework are presented in Section IV.

Section V provides a summary of the original contributions and discusses future work.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

1) Preventive Determination and Avoidance of DDoS Attack with SDN over the IoT Networks

Abstract: The Internet of Things (IoT) is growing increasingly along with the development of security issues. The IoT system is unable in protecting against ransomware and various forms of malicious threats. The way a vast number of IoT devices are treated is uncomfortable and insecure. Security problems have become increasingly important with the spread of IoT devices. The Software-Defined Networking (SDN) paradigm provides a way to control IoT devices securely. For the IoT paradigm, we have suggested a general system for detecting and mitigating Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks using an SDN. The proposed architecture consists of a pool of controllers comprising SDN controllers, IoT gateway-integrated. Also, we have offered an IoT DDoS attack detection and mitigation algorithm attached to the proposed SDN IoT platform. Finally, the proposed algorithm shows the experimental results that have improved performance and the proposed architecture adapts to heterogeneous and fragile devices to enhance IoT security.

2) IoT-Based DDoS Attack Detection and Mitigation Using the Edge of SDN

Abstract: Nowadays, the Internet of Things (IoT) has developed rapidly and changed people's life into a more convenient style. However, a huge number of vulnerable IoT devices are exploited to constitute botnet by many attackers, which forms a serious problem for network security. To solve it, we propose a novel detection and mitigation mechanism. In our method, we use Software Defined Networking (SDN), a promising network architecture, for dropping malicious traffic in propagation path to avoid avalanche effect on the victim server in the traditional network. For the existing works, a lot of time and resources are wasted in using the controller of SDN to detect attacks. Unlike them, we take the features of IoT traffic into consideration and utilize the edge computing to provide local services by putting detection and mitigation method into the OpenFlow (OF) switches of IoT. This achieves a distributed anomaly detection to detect and respond IoT-based DDoS attacks in real time, and avoids the overload of the controller. Machine learning is used in the OF switches with around 99% precision.

Experimental results demonstrate that our method is capable to mitigate IoT-based DDoS attacks in a short time.

3) An Efficient Counter-Based DDoS Attack Detection Framework Leveraging Software Defined IoT (SD-IoT)

Abstract: The Internet of things (IoT) introduces emerging applications (i.e., smart homes, smart cities, smart health, and smart grid) that assist the traditional infrastructure environments to be connected with smart objects. Things are connected with the Internet and numerous new IoT devices are developing at a rapid pace. As these smart objects are connected and able to communicate with each other in unprotected environments; therefore, the whole communication ecosystem requires security solutions at different levels. IoT technology possesses unique characteristics with various resource constraints and heterogeneous network protocol requirements, unlike traditional networks. The attacker exploits numerous security vulnerabilities of an IoT infrastructure, to generate a DDoS attack. The increase in DDoS attacks has made it important to address the consequences which imply in the IoT industry. This research proposes an SD-IoT based framework that provides security services to the IoT network. We developed a C-DAD (Counter-based DDoS Attack Detection) application that is based on counter values of different network parameters, which helps to detect DDoS attack successfully. C-DAD is a dynamic and programmable solution, and is deeply tested with different network parameters. The algorithm demonstrates a good performance with better results through SDN. Moreover, the proposed framework detects the attack efficiently in a minimum amount of time and with lesser consumption of CPU and memory resources.

4) A DDoS attack detection based on deep learning in software-defined Internet of things

Abstract: With the popularity of Internet of Things (IoT) applications, security has become extremely important. A recent distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attack revealed vulnerabilities that are prevalent in IoT, and many IoT devices accidentally contributed to the DDoS attack. software-defined network provides a way to securely manage IoT devices. In this paper, we first present a general framework for software-defined Internet of Things (SD-IoT). The proposed framework consists of a SD-IoT controller, SD-IoT switches integrated with an IoT gateway, and IoT devices. We then propose a

deep learning detection algorithm based on time series using the proposed SD-IoT framework. Finally, experimental results show that the proposed algorithm has good performance.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

Recently, relevant AI-based studies have been presented for DDoS attack detection in Software-Defined IoT (SD-IoT) networks, where SDN was used to improve the security aspects of IoT networks. A DDoS detection solution for an SDN-based IoT network, called LEDEM, was suggested in [18]. The main issue with this model is its lack of adaptability, as LEDEM uses only one classification method and is incapable of dealing with various types of DDoS attacks. Yin et al. [19] proposed a broad architecture for the SD IoT. The proposed SD-IoT architecture analyzes IoT network traffic and detects DDoS attacks based on the network attributes.

The SD-IoT is further constrained by insufficient ML-based categorization algorithms. Xie et al. [20] employed traffic-flow patterns to identify DDoS attacks. This solution shows efficient DDoS information detection with a comparably low overhead compared with other approaches. However, this solution falls short when dealing with heavy network traffic, necessitating the implementation of a more sophisticated security solution. In [21], a new SVM-based security mechanism for IoT networks was proposed. Their model uses learning algorithms for both observing and reacting agents. Their proposed method achieved a general accuracy rate of 99.71% for anomaly identification. The authors of [22] suggested a feed-forward neural network model for attack detection in IIoT networks. The proposed model performed well in terms of accuracy; however, the dataset was not designed for the IIoT domain

Ullah and Mahmoud [23] developed a new anomaly-based detection system for IoT networks. They devised a multiclass classification technique using a convolutional neural network (CNN) algorithm. This classification technique was admirably performed. However, ML approaches are preferred in intrusion detection systems (IDSs) for implementing highly secure capabilities [24]. The authors of [24] examined several ML models to conduct both binary and multiclass classification. They concluded that, compared with other classifiers, the XGBoost technique produced higher performance outcomes. Another CNN-based DDoS attack detection system

for IoT networks, which restricts attacks at the source end, was proposed by the authors of [25].

They evaluated the proposed CNN using the freely accessible dataset CIC-DDoS2019 [26]. Two test cases were used to obtain the performance results; however, this dataset was insufficient for analyzing the behavior of IoT network traffic. Using a recurrent neural network (RNN), Yousuf and Mir [27] proposed an algorithm called DALCNN. DALCNN employs OpenDayLight (ODL) as a suitable SDN controller to address the problem of identifying DDoS attacks in IoT. The gap in DALCNN is that the RNN algorithm was trained using the NSL-KDD dataset, which is unfortunately inadequate for IoT network traffic characteristics. Another detection mechanism for abnormalities in IoT environments was proposed by Alanazi and Aljuhani [28].

The proposed mechanism uses several ML techniques for feature selection and an ensemble learning approach for traffic classification. Numerous constraints were considered in this study. For instance, detection accuracy may be affected by employing custom datasets instead of real-time IIoT traffic. Another problem is that obsolete datasets are restricted to particular types of cyber attacks and cannot recognize contemporary attack scenarios.

Another RNN-based deep learning solution termed “Deep Defense” was proposed by Yuan et al. [29] for detecting DDoS attacks in IoT. This solution employs a series of consecutive network packets to extract low-level features to discriminate between normal and attack packets. However, the authors still need to test their model under numerous real time scenarios. A Deep Neural Network (DNN) approach was proposed in [30] to identify DDoS attack in SDN scenarios. The tests results show that the Deep IDS system is a workable solution with a low network load. The proposed approach does not affect the functionality of the POX controller. Furthermore, the authors needed to improve the model to obtain better detection rates with low false alarm rates across multiple Open Flow Controllers. Zhang et al. [31] presented a technique for detecting low rate (LR) DDoS attacks based on the Power Spectral Density (PSD). In [31], an SVM model was used to extract features from the KDD99 dataset.

DISADVANTAGES

- The system never proposes a new double-check mapping function called DCMF, which is used to provide early attack detection at the switch level.
- An existing system has the following problems 1) missing values replacement, 2) encoding categorical data, and 3) feature scaling.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed framework consisted of four modules: three detection modules and one mitigation module. The first module uses a small window size of 32 packets. This window size was then employed in the third detection module to achieve earlier and more efficient attack detection. The second detection module presents a new mapping function to help detect DDoS attacks at the data plane level. The third module provides an ML-based detection application that is implemented and deployed at the controller level. The last module is a mitigation technique that operates at both switch and controller levels. Most related research uses a conventional, stateless approach to design detection and mitigation processes. The switch scans its flow table to match the incoming packets. If no match was found, the packets were treated as new and routed to the controller for processing. However, this approach lacks scalability and efficiency. In this paper, we make use of the aforementioned “Stateful SDN,” where the switches are given stateful packet analysis privileges by the SDN network. Therefore, when new packets arrive at the network, the switch considers the packets that have already been received in addition to the new packet features.

ADVANTAGES

- The proposed FMDADM framework employs feature engineering to identify DDoS attacks using only five new computed features. The model can successfully overcome the over-fitting problem and provides a good fit as a result.
- The second detection module, which uses a novel proposed mapping function called DCMF, provides two crucial features:- (a) detecting the attack at the data plane level before overwhelming the controller, and (b) discriminating between attack traffic and flash crowds. As a result, the controller has an extra layer of protection against the attack.

- A small 32-packet window size is used for feature extraction in the third detection module. The three detection modules resulted in a reduction in the amount of time needed for training, testing, and detection.
- FMDADM effectively detects DDoS in multi-node attack scenarios. This is a crucial area of strength for the proposed framework because it is generally known that conventional defenses fall short in the face of these attack scenarios.
- FMDADM protects both local and remote IoT nodes by preventing infections from spreading to the ISP level. By protecting the controller and remote nodes in this form, we can stop DDoS attacks before they reach the Internet.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture

5. ALGORITHMS

5.1 DECISION TREE CLASSIFIERS

Decision tree classifiers are used successfully in many diverse areas. Their most important feature is the capability of capturing descriptive decision making knowledge from the supplied data. Decision tree can be generated from training sets. The procedure for such generation based on the set of objects (S), each belonging to one of the classes C1, C2... Ck is as follows:

Step 1. If all the objects in S belong to the same class, for example Ci, the decision tree for S consists of a leaf labeled with this class

Step 2. Otherwise, let T be some test with possible outcomes O_1, O_2, \dots, O_n . Each object in S has one outcome for T so the test partitions S into subsets S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n where each object in S_i has outcome O_i for T . T becomes the root of the decision tree and for each outcome O_i we build a subsidiary decision tree by invoking the same procedure recursively on the set S_i .

5.2 LOGISTIC REGRESSION CLASSIFIERS

Logistic regression analysis studies the association between a categorical dependent variable and a set of independent (explanatory) variables. The name logistic regression is used when the dependent variable has only two values, such as 0 and 1 or Yes and No. The name multinomial logistic regression is usually reserved for the case when the dependent variable has three or more unique values, such as Married, Single, Divorced, or Widowed. Although the type of data used for the dependent variable is different from that of multiple regression, the practical use of the procedure is similar. Logistic regression competes with discriminate analysis as a method for analyzing categorical-response variables. Many statisticians feel that logistic regression is more versatile and better suited for modeling most situations than is discriminate analysis. This is because logistic regression does not assume that the independent variables are normally distributed, as discriminate analysis does. This program computes binary logistic regression and multinomial logistic regression on both numeric and categorical independent variables. It reports on the regression equation as well as the goodness of fit, odds ratios, confidence limits, likelihood, and deviance. It performs a comprehensive residual analysis including diagnostic residual reports and plots. It can perform an independent variable subset selection search, looking for the best regression model with the fewest independent variables. It provides confidence intervals on predicted values and provides ROC curves to help determine the best cutoff point for classification. It allows you to validate your results by automatically classifying rows that are not used during the analysis.

5.3 SVM

In classification tasks a discriminate machine learning technique aims at finding, based on an independent and identically distributed (iid) training dataset, a discriminate function that can correctly predict labels for newly acquired instances. Unlike generative

machine learning approaches, which require computations of conditional probability distributions, a discriminate classification function takes a data point x and assigns it to one of the different classes that are a part of the classification task. Less powerful than generative approaches, which are mostly used when prediction involves outlier detection, discriminate approaches require fewer computational resources and less training data, especially for a multidimensional feature space and when only posterior probabilities are needed. From a geometric perspective, learning a classifier is equivalent to finding the equation for a multidimensional surface that best separates the different classes in the feature space. SVM is a discriminate technique, and, because it solves the convex optimization problem analytically, it always returns the same optimal hyper plane parameter—in contrast to genetic algorithms (GAs) or perceptions, both of which are widely used for classification in machine learning. For perceptions, solutions are highly dependent on the initialization and termination criteria. For a specific kernel that transforms the data from the input space to the feature space, training returns uniquely defined SVM model parameters for a given training set, whereas the perception and GA classifier models are different each time training is initialized. The aim of GAs and perceptions is only to minimize error during training, which will translate into several hyper planes' meeting this requirement.

5.4 RANDOM FOREST

Random forests or random decision forests are an ensemble learning method for classification, regression and other tasks that operates by constructing a multitude of decision trees at training time. For classification tasks, the output of the random forest is the class selected by most trees. For regression tasks, the mean or average prediction of the individual trees is returned. Random decision forests correct for decision trees' habit of over fitting to their training set. Random forests generally outperform decision trees, but their accuracy is lower than gradient boosted trees. However, data characteristics can affect their performance. The first algorithm for random decision forests was created in 1995 by Tin Kam Ho[1] using the random subspace method, which, in Ho's formulation, is a way to implement the "stochastic discrimination" approach to classification proposed by Eugene Kleinberg. An extension of the algorithm was developed by Leo Breiman and Adele Cutler,

who registered "Random Forests" as a trademark in 2006 (as of 2019, owned by Minitab, Inc.). The extension combines Breiman's "bagging" idea and random selection of features, introduced first by Ho[1] and later independently by Amit and Geman[13] in order to construct a collection of decision trees with controlled variance. Random forests are frequently used as "blackbox" models in businesses, as they generate reasonable predictions across a wide range of data while requiring little configuration.

6. RESULTS

6.1 Output Screens

Fig 6.1 Home Page

In above screen is the Home page

Fig 6.2 Accuracy for different ml algorithms

In above screen shows the accuracy for the different ml algorithms.

Fig 6.3 Bar Chart for different ml algorithms accuracy
 In above screen shows the barchart for the different ml algorithms accuracy.

Fig 6.4 Prediction Result

In above screen shows the prediction result for the fraud transactions in banking.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced FMDADM, an ML-based DDOS detection, and mitigation framework for SDN-enabled IOT networks. The proposed framework comprises three detection modules and a mitigation module. The first module employs a 32-packet window size used for feature extraction in the third detection module. The second detection module introduces a novel mapping function called DCMF. The DCMF provides two crucial features:- (a) detecting the attack at the data plane level before overwhelming the controller, and (b) discriminating between attack traffic and flash crowds. As a result, the controller has an extra layer of protection against the attack. The third detection module employs feature engineering to identify DDOS attacks using only five new computed features. As a result, the model gives a good fit and can successfully handle the over-fitting problem. The three detection modules resulted in a reduction in the amount of time needed for training, testing, and detection. We thoroughly tested the proposed framework by employing trained BLR, GNB, SVM, KNN, DT, and RF models to assess their performance outcomes and select the best model. The RF model performed best across all ten evaluation metrics. Three different test scenarios were used to evaluate the performance of the proposed framework. According to the experiments, the FMDADM can detect DDOS with high accuracy in multi-node attack scenarios. This is a crucial area of strength for the proposed framework because it is generally known that conventional defenses fall short in the face of these attack scenarios. The proposed

framework is designed to prevent local DDOS attacks produced by IOT Bot nets inside compromised LANs from propagating to the ISP level. By protecting the controller and remote nodes in this form, we can stop DDOS attacks before they can reach the Internet. The proposed FMDADM framework can effectively identify DDOS attacks at both high and low rates. The experimental results show that the proposed framework performed better than most cutting-edge solutions currently available with the following benchmarks for accuracy, precision, F-measure, recall, specificity, negative predictive value, false positive rate, false detection rate, false negative rate, and average detection time: 99.79%, 99.09%, 99.43%, 99.77%, 99.79%, 99.95%, 00.21%, 00.91%, 00.23%, and 2.64 μ s. In the future, we plan to deploy and evaluate the proposed framework in a multi-controller SD-IOT environment. Additionally, we plan to test the proposed framework with other controllers to determine which one works best for the IOT network. In addition, we will test increasingly sophisticated test scenarios. Finally, the detection of more attack types on an SDN-based IoT network may be added to this study.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] A. E. Omolara, A. Alabdulatif, O. I. Abiodun, M. Alawida, A. Alabdulatif, W. H. Alshoura, and H. Arshad, "The Internet of Things security: A survey encompassing unexplored areas and new insights," *Comput. Secur.*, vol. 112, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 102494, doi: 10.1016/j.cose.2021.102494.
- [2] K. K. Kumar, S. G. B. Kumar, S. G. R. Rao and S. S. J. Sydulu, "Safe and high secured ranked keyword searchover an outsourced cloud data," 2017 International Conference on Inventive Computing and Informatics (ICICI), Coimbatore, India, 2017, pp. 20-25, doi: 10.1109/ICICI.2017.8365348.
- [3] I. H. Sarker, A. I. Khan, Y. B. Abushark, and F. Alsolami, "Internet of Things (IoT) security intelligence: A comprehensive overview, machine learning solutions and research directions," *Mobile Netw. Appl.*, pp. 1–17, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11036-022-01937-3.
- [4] V. Mothukuri, P. Khare, R. M. Parizi, S. Pouriyeh, A. Dehghantaha, and G. Srivastava, "Federated-learning-based anomaly detection for IoT security attacks," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 2545–2554, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2021.3077803.
- [5] M. Azrou, J. Mabrouki, A. Guezzaz, and A. Kanwal, "Internet of Things security: Challenges and key issues," *Secur. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 2021, pp. 1–11, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/5533843.
- [6] A. Imteaj, U. Thakker, S. Wang, J. Li, and M. H. Amini, "A survey on federated learning for resource-constrained IoT devices," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1–24, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2021.3095077.
- [7] K. K. Kommineni and A. Prasad, "A Review on Privacy and Security Improvement Mechanisms in MANETs", *Int J Intell Syst Appl Eng*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 90–99, Dec. 2023.
- [8] S. Siddiqui, S. Hameed, S. A. Shah, I. Ahmad, A. Aneiba, D. Draheim, and S. Dustdar, "Towards software-defined networkingbased IoT frameworks: A systematic literature review, taxonomy, open challenges and prospects," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 70850–70901, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3188311.
- [9] B. Isyaku, K. B. A. Bakar, F. A. Ghaleb, and A. Al-Nahari, "Dynamic routing and failure recovery approaches for efficient resource utilization in OpenFlow-SDN: A survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 121791–121815, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3222849.
- [10] X. Zhang, L. Cui, K. Wei, F. P. Tso, Y. Ji, and W. Jia, "A survey on stateful data plane in software defined networks," *Comput. Netw.*, vol. 184, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 107597, doi: 10.1016/j.comnet.2020.107597.
- [11] J. Galeano-Brajones, J. Carmona-Murillo, J. F. Valenzuela-Valdés, and F. Luna-Valero, "Detection and mitigation of dos and DDoS attacks in IoTbased stateful SDN: An experimental approach," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 3, p. 816, 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20030816.
- [12] A. Mahmood, C. Casetti, C. F. Chiasserini, P. Giaccone, and J. Härrri, "Efficient caching through stateful SDN in named data networking," *Trans. Emerg. Telecommun. Technol.*, vol. 29, no. 1, p. e3271, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1002/ett.3271.

[13] Kiran Kumar Kommineni, Ratna Babu Pilli, K. Tejaswi, P. Venkata Siva, Attention-based Bayesian inferential imagery captioning maker, Materials Today: Proceedings, 2023, , ISSN 2214-7853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.05.231>.

[14] A. Rahman, M. J. Islam, A. Montieri, M. K. Nasir, M. M. Reza, S. S. Band, A. Pescapè, M. Hasan, M. Sookhak, and A. Mosavi, "SmartBlock-SDN: An optimized blockchain-SDN framework for resource management in IoT," IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 28361–28376, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3058244.

15. Dr.Venkata Kishore Kumar Rejeti, et.al, IOT - ENABLED CYBER PHYSICAL SYSTEMS TOWARDS CYBER-ATTACK DETECTION AND ATTRIBUTION, Journal of Data Acquisition and Processing Vol. 38 (4) 2023, ISSN: 1004-9037, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.777, <https://sjcjycl.cn/>

16. Dr.Venkata Kishore Kumar Rejeti, et.al, "A Systematic Approach for Reconstruction of an Image Using Classification Techniques", International journal for innovative engineering and management research, DOI: 10.48047/IJEMR/V12/ISSUE 01/78, Volume 12, Issue 01, Jan 2023 ISSN 2456 – 5083, Pages: 840-850.

17. J. Gera, Dr.Venkata Kishore Kumar Rejeti, J. N. C. Sekhar and A. S. Shankar, "Distributed Denial of Service Attack Prevention from Traffic Flow for Network Performance Enhancement," 2021 2nd International Conference on Smart Electronics and Communication (ICOSEC), Trichy, India, 2021, pp. 406-413, doi: 10.1109/ICOSEC51865.2021.9591974.